

TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACTIVATION AND INTENSIFICATION OF STUDENTS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10937640>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 3rd April 2024

Accepted: 4th April 2024

Published: 6th April 2024

KEYWORDS

intensification of the learning process, Russian language, online resources, gamification, modern and innovative technologies

ABSTRACT

This article discusses technologies for activating and intensifying the activities of students in Russian language classes. The importance of activating students' internal knowledge reserves, increasing their motivation during the educational process and using gaming technologies and exercises, the need to develop and implement a new integrated approach to learning, which will take into account the capabilities of the Internet and the features of the educational process taking place online, are shown.

The principle of student activity in the learning process has been and remains one of the main ones in didactics. This concept means a quality of activity that is characterized by a high level of motivation, a conscious need to acquire knowledge and skills, effectiveness and compliance with social norms. This kind of activity in itself occurs infrequently; it is a consequence of targeted managerial pedagogical influences and the organization of the pedagogical environment, i.e. applied pedagogical technology.

Any technology has means that activate and intensify the activities of students, but in some technologies, these means constitute the main idea and the basis for the effectiveness of the results. In order to understand the topic of the article, you need to determine the meaning of all components:

“Pedagogical technologies are a set of psychological and pedagogical attitudes that determine a special set and arrangement of forms, methods, methods, teaching techniques, educational means: it is the organizational and methodological tools of the pedagogical process”.

The form of teaching is the external expression of the coordinated activity of the teacher and students, carried out in a certain order and mode.

The method of teaching is the implementation of the educational process as a whole, through a certain structure of general organizational forms, with one of them being the leading one.

Means of training and education - devices, equipment, including sports equipment and inventory, instruments (including musical), educational and visual aids, computers, information and telecommunication networks, hardware, software and audiovisual tools, printed and electronic educational and information resources and other material objects necessary for organizing educational activities.

Student - an individual who is mastering an educational program.

Activation is a constantly ongoing process of encouraging energetic, purposeful learning, overcoming passive and stereotypical activity, decline and stagnation in mental work.

Intensification of training is the transfer of a larger volume of educational information to students, with a constant duration of training without reducing the requirements for the quality of knowledge.

Educational activity of students is a type of activity aimed at mastering the language in the process of learning, communication of students with each other, the teacher, native speakers, as well as in the process of independent work.

In connection with the above, we can say that pedagogical technologies based on the activation and intensification of students' activities are an active form of organizing student learning, using certain resources, with minimal time expenditure and the maximum amount of information. At the same time, the requirements for the quality of acquired knowledge are not reduced.

Thus, it is advisable to include gamification as a way to intensify the educational process, due to which there is an increase in motivation for learning the Russian language by ionophones. Games in Russian language lessons provide variability and dynamism in students' work, increasing the efficiency of mastering new material through the formation of communicative competence and the use of speech and mental mechanisms. Any game exercises represent a multi-level approach to learning, since they force students to use the Russian language as a means of communication and expression of their own ideas and thoughts and as a tool for solving the task posed in the task. In an easy and relaxed manner, the student is immersed in the environment of using natural speech structures and widely used vocabulary. He has no choice to refuse or remain silent, since he must fully participate in the game, express his opinion, find understanding by communicating with other students using the Russian language. That is why, in our opinion, communicative games play an important role in the process of intensifying students' activities in Russian language classes, being the basis for presenting and consolidating new lexical and grammatical material at the level of skills and abilities.

Games can also be used during the development, for example, of the topic "Verbs of Movement". They are necessary in order to slightly reduce the emphasis on the complexity of a given topic, increase students' motivation, and help them feel free when using a particular verb.

The student draws a card from the deck on which is written a sentence with a verb of motion (Go to the window - Подойти к окну). He reads it to one of his classmates, who will have to perform the indicated action. It is worth saying that when introducing this game in Russian language lessons, it is very important to physically move around the classroom (Go into the classroom, Leave the classroom, Go to the blackboard - Зайди в аудиторию, Выйди из аудитории, Подойди к доске). This will help students master basic phrases for

communication and better remember in what cases a certain verb of motion is used, what prefix and meaning it contains.

In addition to a fairly active game of moving around the classroom, the teacher can use the cards in another game exercise. Students receive 3-4 cards on which, on one side, a specific verb of motion is written. A presenter is selected from among foreign students and given a whole set of phrases written on a piece of paper. He reads out these phrases one by one, and the rest of the students must show a card with a verb of motion that can be used together with this phrase or sentence. During this game, the skills of using verbs of motion in the most common life situations are honed. The atmosphere of competition, freedom and lightness increases the motivation of foreign students and has a positive effect on the quick and effective mastery of a new topic.

As examples of the use of innovative technologies in activating and intensifying the activities of students in Russian language classes, the following Internet platforms and resources can be identified:

a) Wordwall website designer (<https://wordwall.net>). It is possible to create various types of exercises related to memorization and training of use in speech. For example, there are tasks in which foreign students need to select a card number (from 1 to 20), behind which a certain task is hidden. It must be used in speech: the student composes his own example of a sentence, the context of which must correspond to the specified word.

b) Website <https://en.islcollective.com> with worksheets on grammar topics. This resource presents a whole variety of exercises that are related to practice and mastery of even complex topics when learning the Russian language. In addition, a special section with videos was developed, the topics of which correspond to various grammatical and lexical sections of the Russian language. So, when watching a video about the traditions of the Russian people, you need to complete the tasks that pop up below, where you must insert the appropriate words according to their meaning into the specified sentence.

c) Some noteworthy courses and online platforms that offer comprehensive mastery of the Russian language include the Russian portal "Survival Russian"; the American website "Between Us" (<https://mezhdunami.org>) and the Spanish educational resource "Red Kalinka" (www.redkalinka.com).

d) It is also worth noting a number of online games hosted on special educational platforms, which provide the opportunity to make the process of learning the Russian language more fruitful, to consolidate already acquired and new speech skills in an easy game form. Many similar online games are posted on the educational portal called "Russian Online" (<https://ruskiyonline.com>): these are exercises in the format "Find the extra word", "Solve the rebus", "Unravel the word". In addition, online quizzes created on the Kahoot platform (<https://kahoot.com>) are very successful. This resource provides the opportunity to create an interactive, colorful and dynamic quiz, which will allow foreign students to test their knowledge and compete with other ionophores in real time.

Thus, the organization of training using pedagogical technologies based on the activation and intensification of student activity is undoubtedly complex. To successfully implement technology in teaching and learning, it is necessary to consider the pedagogical challenges that arise during its implementation. It is important that teachers perceive technology in education as part of the pedagogical process. It is necessary that teachers understand the pedagogical

principles governing the use of modern and innovative technology in teaching and learning. The content of educational technology should be systematized. Evaluation of student activities, lesson objectives, teaching methods, etc. should be presented. At each stage of technology implementation, detailed content of the activity must be presented. Even the smallest stage in the implementation of pedagogical learning technology can affect the planned result.

REFERENCES:

1. Solieva, Z. B., & Javburieva, R. USE OF GAMES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 18.
2. Солиева, З. Б. ПРОБЛЕМА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ СЛОВА И СПОСОБЫ ЕЕ РЕШЕНИЯ. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 27.
3. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). Анализ человеческой психики в повестях. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
4. Эшматова, Ю. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПСИХОЛОГИЗМА В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ. *ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMYI JURNALI*, 2(11), 155-161.
5. Boymaxmatovna, E. Y. (2022). WRITER'S SKILL AND LANDSCAPE IMAGE. *ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMYI JURNALI*, 2(11), 143-146.
6. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). О 'ZGA TILLI GURUHLARDA SHE'RLARNING JANR XUSUSIYATLARINI FARQLASHGA O'RGATISH. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
7. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). ЎЗБЕК АЁЛИ РУҲИАТИНИНГ ЁРИТИЛИШИДА ЯНГИ ҚИРРАЛАРНИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
8. МАМАТҚУЛОВ, В. (2024). О 'ZBEKISTON JANUBIY VILOYATLARIDA SANOAT KORXONALARINING TASHKIL ETILISHI VA HUDUDLAR SANOATINING IXTISOSLASHUVI JARAYONINING TARIXIY TAHLILI (1930-1950 yy). *News of UzMU journal*, 1(1.2. 1).
9. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). INDUSTRIAL MEASURES IN UZBEKISTAN 1925-1954 AND THEIR RESULTS (in the case of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions). *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 195-200.
10. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD INDUSTRIES IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND CONSEQUENCES. *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 188-194.
11. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). CONFLICT SITUATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING INDUSTRY PERSONNEL IN SURKHANDARYA AND KASHKADARYA REGIONS: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS (1925-1950). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 221-225.
12. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). THE EMERGENCE OF THE GAS-SULFUR INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT HISTORY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF KASHKADARYA REGION). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 217-220.

13. Rustamkulovna, S. T. (2022). SOCIAL FACTORS OF ETHNOCULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 622-626.
14. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2022). ЗАМОНАВИЙ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ФАЛСАФАНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ ВА МУАММОЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(9), 657-664.
15. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2021). ВЛИЯНИЕ ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 НА СОСТОЯНИЕ ЭТНОКУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *Новые вызовы новой науки: опыт теоретического и эмпирического анализа* (pp. 176-183).
16. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).
17. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).
18. Холдарова, Ф. Т. (2018). Стратегия повышения эффективности политических переговоров Узбекистана в регионе Центральной Азии. In *Theory and practice of scientific research* (pp. 268-270).
19. Ugli, I. J. T., Tuxtabayevna, K. F., & Ugli, I. S. T. (2020). Comparison of Similes and Metaphors in Translations (In Act of Beneficent Knowledge). *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(05).
20. Очилова, Г. А., Жумаева, Ш. С., & Курбонова, М. Б. (2019). Политика межнациональных отношений и толерантность в Узбекистане. *Наука, образование и культура*, (9 (43)), 15-18.
21. Жумаева, Ш. С., & Очилова, Г. А. (2019). ТВОРЧЕСКАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ И ЕЁ ГУМАНИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ. *Научное знание современности*, (2), 5-10.
22. Навои, А. (2016). Проблема этических норм развития науки в трудах мыслителей средневековой Средней Азии. *Молодой учёный*, 6, 670.
23. Жумаева, Ш. С. (2023). АХБОРОТ ХАВФСИЗЛИГИ ВА МАФКУРАВИЙ ҲИМОЯ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5 SPECIAL), 286-290.
24. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). The Culture of Reading as a Phenomenon of Spiritual Life. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 84-87.
25. Taxirovna, A. S. LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS, 2023/2/c12.
26. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
27. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories, *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany)*.
28. Mamatkulov, B. (2021). Conflicts of the process of the industrial staff training in the soviet period. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 507-510.

29. Mamatkulov, B. (2021, November). A New Interpretation of Industry in Uzbekistan During Independence. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 158-161).
30. Маматкулов, Б. (2023). О 'ZBEKISTONDA GAZ-OLTINGUGURT SANOATINING YUZAGA KELISHI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA). *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(12/1).
31. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). Combination of Mythological, Religious and Philosophical Worldviews.
32. Алиева, З. Р. (2020). Роль дистанционного обучения в методике преподавания русского языка как иностранного. *Молодой ученый*, (35), 176-178.
33. Алиева, З. Р. (2024). ТЕОРИЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКИ. *SCHOLAR*, 2(5), 121-126.
34. Kakharova, D. S. (2020). CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(2), 337-342.
35. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Ҳалим қизи.
36. Ахмедов, О. С. (2010). Лексико-семантические проблемы при переводе с английского языка налоговых и таможенных терминов. *Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики*, (1-2), 18-21.
37. Ахмедов, О. С. (2014). Калькирование в налоговой и таможенной терминосистеме узбекского языка. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (3 (332)), 12-15.